

The Inspiration through World Skills Competition on Tourism & Hotel Management Curriculum Construction and Student Cultivating

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Abstract

In this paper, we employ the real case and feelings of tourism and hotel management students to participate in the "World Competition", which reflects how the hotel industry has implemented the "banquet service standard", and also lays a solid foundation for future student's learning and corporate practicing. With the continuous improvement of "Chinese Services" and the application of practical teaching, the training goals of tourism management personnel in vocational colleges have changed. The launch of the World Skills Competition fits this trend and promotes the reform and development of the hotel management talent training model. The World Skills Competition is hailed as the "World Skills Olympics". China participated in this project for the first time in 2015 (43th), and won consecutive gold awards in 2017 (44th) and 2019 (45th). Awards and restaurant service excellence awards have achieved zero breakthroughs in medals. The four majors covering cooking, baking, restaurant service, and hospitality of the hotel management major are all competitions in the personal and social service areas of the World Skills Competition. From August 22-27, 2019, the 45th World Skills Competition was held in Kazan, Russia. The Chinese delegation won a total of 16 gold medals, 14 silver medals, 5 bronze medals and 17 winning prizes in this competition. The gold medal list, medal list, and group total score are the first. China will host the 46th Shanghai World Skills Competition in 2021. In the future, we should focus on increasing international cooperation with members of the World Skills Organization, and closely follow hotel professional skills projects. It is hoped that the World Skills Competition will become the vane of the hotel management professional training and the level of colleges and universities. It is also prepared data, case study and even positive thing king ways for the constant education research and ability-centered way.

Keywords: Hotel service; skill competition; vocational talent training; change; development trend.

1. Introduction

The World Skills Competition is known as the "World Skills Olympics", which mainly covers six categories: art creation and fashion, information and communication technology, architecture and technology, social and personal services, manufacturing and engineering technology, transportation and logistics. The first World Skills Competition was held in Madrid, Spain, in 1950. At that time, only 24 teams from 2 teams competed on the same stage. In 1953, European countries began to join the World Skills Competition one after another. Since its development, it has increased to 68 teams in the 44th World Skills Competition. The World Skills Competition is

not only a platform for global young people to communicate and compete, but also a platform for the display of global advanced equipment, which has also played a role in the construction of hotel management.

The author personally participated in the national selection contest for the 45th World Race Restaurant Service and Hotel Reception Event, and is also a member of the Culinary Event Expert Group. As one of the participating members of the Beijing team, the author¹ participated in the 45th World Skills Beijing competition preparations, questions, and group competitions with new events were analyzed. The individual requirements and actual questions of the contestants in the technical documents were analyzed, and with the hotel reception project competition field of the 2019 World Skills Competition and the added events and the on-the-spot situation, the future development trend of the project will be forecasted.

1.1 Project Description

Globalization, changes in socio-economic and population flows, and the convenience and speed of transportation have greatly promoted the rapid growth of tourism and the prosperity of business travel. As a result, travel and tourism play an important role in social and economic growth around the world.

Different types, different sizes, different brands, and various styles of hotels provide accommodation and a series of standardized services for guests around the world, creating a warm atmosphere and a life experience of being at home and enjoying business travel. Hotel quality service and price positioning usually correspond to each other effectively. The international star-hotel system can provide guests with a reasonable and general reference value, even a moment of truth. At the same time, in the process of brand building and marketing, hotels can make product culture recommendations that match their own characteristics according to their location, historical background, architectural characteristics and target customers.

The hotel receptionist is the key image window of the hotel. The hotel reception area is the main place where hotel staff communicate with guests. The guests' first impression of the hotel mainly comes from the hotel reception staff. Its professional image, artistic expression, service quality, and polite agility will affect and determine the satisfaction of guests during their stay in the hotel. Whether positive or negative differentiation will affect the quality reputation and return rate of hotel services.

Hotel reception staff mainly work at the front desk of the hotel, which must fully display the hotel's style and taste, as well as personal good professionalism. Therefore, hotel reception staff need to be proficient in and properly use a variety of business knowledge and skills, including: local and relevant tourism cultural information knowledge, good written English and spoken expressions, computer and Internet application skills, good etiquette, decent occupation Dress code, good communication skills, ability to resolve emergencies, guest relations, cashier knowledge, booking procedures, inquiries, check-in and check-out. Hotel reception is a truly international and global profession.

1.2 Assessment Purposes and Documents

The purpose of the national service competition for the hotel service skills competition is to show the advantages of the current and future hotel service industry. Quality service skills; Selecting outstanding players for the 45th World Skills Contest and Organizing national training teams. The technical work document of this project only contains relevant information about the technical work of the project. In addition to reading this document, this skill project competition must be used in conjunction with other relevant documents. Each referee and player must read and understand this technical note. The computer front-end operating system is based on the OPERA system.

2. The Abilities the Competitor Needs to Have

2.1 The Necessary Abilities

This competition is a demonstration and evaluation of the service skills of the hotel lobby. Only Testing the ability to operate the skills. Participants are required to demonstrate hotel lobby service skills in accordance with the lobby service standards (or requirements).

Including: knowledge of local and related tourism culture information, good written English and spoken language, computer and internet application skills, good etiquette, proper professional dress, ability to solve emergencies, good communication and expression skills, guest relations, cashier knowledge, booking procedures, inquiries, check-in and check-out.(For details, please read the technical description of the hotel reception project of the 45th World Skills Competition, TD Hotel Reception from 2.2 WORLDSKILLS STANDARDS SPECIFICATION)

2.2 The Other Important Needs

Such as good attitude, concerns and kindness, Empathy, caring for others, responsibility, mission, identity etc..

3.The Competition Project

3.1 Competition modules

This competition is a practical operation competition. The test questions refer to the World Skills Competition. The competition content is six modules, specifically:

Module number	Module name		Fraction
A	Personal Image Display		10
B	Tourism Culture Promotion		15
C	Handover Report		10
D	Complaint Handling Techniques		15
E	Booking sales		25
F	Reception check-in		25
Total			100

3.2 Module Brief Description

3.2.1 Module A: Personal Image Display

The contestants appeared in the order of the draw, made a collective appearance, and unified scores. The contestants were required to be full of spirit, natural expressions, smiles, elegant temperament, attention to etiquette, neat and clean clothing, light makeup for women, no beards for men, no long nails, and agility , Beautiful posture, reflecting the temperament of post performance, showing the excellent quality of hotel reception staff, leaving a good first impression to guests, fully reflecting the importance of hotel reception.Through the etiquette image display, the player's image and professional temperament and accomplishment are displayed.

3.2.2 Module B: Tourism Culture Promotion

According to the well-known domestic and foreign travel pictures and background materials provided by the organizing committee, the contestants can describe the scenes they see in English. They can explain according to the local culture, history, tourism, cuisine and cultural traditions. Experiences and referrals allow visitors to better understand the culture of the local culture area. The introduction and explanation can be combined with the local basic culture or the marketing plan designed by the hotel, which can reflect the thoughtfulness and meticulousness of its own marketing from the hotel product marketing and customer service links, and highlight the regional characteristics.

Through the promotion of tourism culture, the player's image and professional temperament and accomplishment will be displayed, and the hotel brand value and visibility will be enhanced.

3.2.3 Module C: Work Handover Report

According to the test paper provided by the contest organizing committee, the handover record form of the corresponding shift is written in English. To reflect the requirements and responsibilities of the front desk of the hotel, ensure that all information is transferred to the next shift during shifts, and respond effectively to accidents. In emergency situations, follow the emergency plan, comply with relevant regulations, comply with the reporting (reporting) process, and effectively ensure priority work. The examination was carried out smoothly, and the examination content involved VIP reception, team check-in, account status, guest illness, emergencies and other hotel common problems. Through the work handover report, the player's word processing ability, communication and teamwork ability were demonstrated.

3.2.4 Module D: Complaint Handling Techniques (Case Analysis)

The theme is to deal with common security problems, settlement problems, accidents, customer relations, and hotel internal communication in hotel reception services. The players use Chinese and English to analyze and answer. To organize answers according to the actual situation of the hotel, but to follow the organizational principles of hotel management, to have internal connections, to have sufficient persuasive power, to detect the ability of players to objectively and keenly find potential problems and complaint handling skills, and be able to apply the hotel's procedures to properly solve the problems. Through complaint handling and inquiry handling, the contestant's ability to solve problems and professionalism are demonstrated.

3.2.5 Module E: Booking Sales

The contestant answers of the guest's call, recording the reservation information appropriately, maximizing the sales related services and facilities according to the availability and cost of the room, reaching an agreement with the guest, accepting the reservation and collecting the deposit according to the hotel's relevant payment regulations, and allocating the room reasonably, Recording additional services or special requirements, and entering booking information into the computer system, talking to guests in English and completing telephone booking tasks. After passing the assessment, the contestant answers of the two guests' calls, handling and solving the problem of booking and inquiring for the guest, and requiring the contestant to use the OPERA software system to handle the booking business for the guest. Skills, showing the player's English communication ability, software application ability and professionalism.

3.2.6 Module F: Reception service

In a role-playing manner, according to the hotel's regulations and procedures, proficiently check-in guests, including: room allocation, document scanning, room card issuance, baggage delivery, deposit deposit, document copying and filing, providing related information consulting and services, etc., and Guest checkout and checkout procedures, advance payment of advance deposits and guest refund processing, correct calculation of sales tax, cash or foreign currency exchange, printing of bills, etc., speaking to guests in English and complete tasks. The contestants took over the walk in guest check-in and performed an up sell service. The assessment content includes (1) OPERA system operation: check-in operation process and check-out operation process, etc.; (2) guests check-in and reception: guests arrive at the hotel after booking, the service staff provides related services by accepting and checking in guests. Checking the proficiency of the players in checking the reservation, OPERA system operation and check-in process; (3) Consulting the reception service, that is, to deal with problems during the stay of the hotel guests, such as: the room card can not open the door, need temporary laundry or services such as short-term baby care are needed. Examining staff in English to deal with emergencies, OPERA system operation skills, etc.

4. Propositional methods

4.1 Propositional methods

The proposition method of this project competition question: part of the public proposition. The content of the contest questions is based on the technical requirements of the 45th World Skills Contest. Before the match, the referee may combine the equipment and materials of the arena, and according to the workflow and method of adjusting the test questions of this project, organize the referees to not exceed the published test questions. 30% modification and adjustment. Then, the referee signs and confirms the final test questions. Final competition test

questions should be announced at the beginning of the official competition (a specific time agreed with the competition area and experts).

This item is an item that needs to be kept confidential before the competition. Announce sample questions (including contest questions, materials, and scoring details) before the game. Before the competition, the organizing committee of the competition shall consult with the referees of the relevant projects in the competition, refer to the 45th World Skills Contest 's test system, published methods and procedures, and combine domestic security work management requirements to formulate and announce test questions to ensure the competition fair and just.

4.2 Propositional plan

The competition is based on the hotel reception project competition module of the 45th World Skills Contest, covering some of the key points of the skills involved in the hotel reception project of the World Skills Contest, keeping the basic technical difficulty of the World Skills Contest as much as possible, and shortening the competition time to test Participants will focus on professional theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and oral English.

5. The scoring rules

The competition scoring table follows the CIS (Contest Information System) format, and the competition-specific scoring system is used to automatically calculate and summarize points. The specific scoring rules are based on each module

5.1 Unified method

Each module has 5-7 referees. Each module removes one highest score, one lowest score, and takes the average value. The average value is the final score of each module. The score is kept to 2 decimal places. Plus, the referee will make a final review.

5.2 Composition and division of referees

The referee team has one referee and several referees. The referee is appointed by the organizing committee, and the referee is recommended by each participating team. The members of the referee team, under the leadership of the referee, are responsible for the technical work of each link of the game.

5.3 Conditions of Referee Service

Referees must have the relevant knowledge and skills required by this project;

Referees must be proficient in listening, speaking, and reading English;

The referee must have at least three years of working experience in the hospitality field or related fields.

5.4 Event analysis

Through the response to the above questions, the contestants are proficient in the comprehensive knowledge and skills of accepting guest reservations, inquiries, concierge services after guests arrive at the store, and reception services.

1. Smiling welcome at the hotel reception, warm greetings, confirming the guest's reservation information, such as: room type, length of stay, number of people, breakfast, etc .; inform the guest of the room rate and timely Upsell.
2. Guests are required to show valid credentials and check photocopies when checking in to the hotel, to allocate rooms, print check-in forms and invite guests to sign, to collect guest deposits correctly, to make and issue cards, to fill out welcome cards, etc. Note that you must answer the guest's questions reasonably at check-in, introduce related service information and reasonably Upsell according to the actual situation. Then, you can organize the guest registration information and guest history file, and note that there is no omission of the booking information.
3. During the check-out process, you need to collect the room card, confirm the room number, and report the check-out. In this step, pay attention to the correct calculation of the guest's consumption, handle the relevant room bills,

correct the check-out, and print the bill. The taxi service and the luggage service ,at last, do not forget to say goodbye to the guests warmly.

Competitors need to have natural expressions, professional standards, and agility to reflect their postal temperament throughout the service; fluent language, standard pronunciation, and clear and accurate expression. According to the hotel industry standards, players will be more welcome if they can provide guests with unexpected services or have new and unique insights on business skills.

6. Summary

As a newly added event, the hotel reception event highlights the common problems held for the first time, that is, due to the different levels of hotel industry development across the country, the differences in the importance of the human society system, and the different preparation times. As a result, there are great differences in the level of contestants. Players in developed coastal areas and developed cities such as Beijing, Shanghai, Guangzhou and other cities have generally shown their due standards. At the same time, we also found that second- and third-tier cities such as Jiangxi, Wuhan, and Changchun have also shown good standards. This competition ranked 2, 3, and 4, which are in line with their provincial, municipal, and human resources bureaus and school leaders. The degree of importance is very relevant.

6.1 Tournament Features

6.1.1 Participants' characteristics

As the World Tour Hotel reception required players to use OPERA English software throughout the game and intelligently communicate and communicate with guests in English, the player's English level is particularly important and the main score point. The World Sai Hotel Hotel requires and emphasizes communication with guests, and requires players to have the ability to communicate and respond on the spot, and more importantly, to solve problems.

The World Championships, The hotel reception event requires that the contestants not be over 21 years old. Therefore, most of the players are students at school. There is a problem that the courses and actual work in the school are not yet connected. Students still lack hotel work, and lack of on-site experience and adaptability during the game.

Performance of Beijing athletes participating in World Competition's Hotel. As one of the participating members of the Beijing team, the writers received the task of the Beijing trials on January 20, 2019. they feel deeply responsible for this event. Under the situation of tight time and heavy tasks, they actively coordinate and communicate with the participating teams. After early contacts, 5 outstanding players from Beijing Vocational College of Labor and Social Security, Beijing Vocational College of Economics and Management, Beijing Vocational College of Agriculture, and Sino-Swedish Hotel Management School of Beijing Second Foreign Language College participated in the Beijing finals. After selecting the outstanding players, after the practice of the Holiday Spirit Hotel and the Hyatt Hotel and the 10-day intensive training of Erwai and Zhongrui, they finally participated in the national competition with the players and achieved good results.

6.2 Innovations:

6.2.1 A test question bank

According to the study and arrangement of the technical documents of the event, a test question bank was prepared. The content of the competition covers three modules: room reservation service, check-in reception and check-out service, and service during the stay (complaints and travel services). Demonstrate the professional image of the players, communicate with customers, handle emergencies, sell products and English language skills. This competition is simulated through real scenes, requires full English operation, and meets the World Skills Competition with high standards. The competition rules, scoring and scoring methods are all adopted in the World Skills Competition.

6.2.2 Contacted hotel professional manager as referee

The simulation guests of this competition are foreign guests. The competition judges use a combination of corporate experts and professional teachers from colleges and universities to invite high-end well-known hotels such as Financial Street International Hotel, Reignwood Fairmont Hotel, Beijing Xihua Business Hotel, etc. Managers act as on-site judges, and experts have more than ten years of hotel work management experience.

6.2.3 The principles of open competition and openness and transparency.

The Beijing World Championship adheres to the principles of open competition and openness and transparency. During the preparation and implementation of the competition, the whole process of photography and video is implemented to monitor and inspect all links; after the competition, special time is reserved to accept written appeals from participating teams and conduct arbitration. The viewing area is set in the competition item, and the audience can watch the player's operation process without disturbing the competition.

6.2.4 Solution to the problem:

- (1) Increasing the practical curriculum for students majoring in hotel management;
- (2) Strengthening the enterprise system under teachers;
- (3) Increasing school-enterprise cooperation and work-study integration, and strive to integrate internships and practical training courses with students' professional matching.
- (4) With the World Championship high-level event platform, we should promote education and teaching reform, promote the design and construction reform of the training room, and build a high-level practical teaching team and theoretical research team. which is:

Enterprise executives, professionals + college teachers, professors = coaching team.

Practice place + theory = base;

Practice + teaching scene = real;

World Sailing Experience + Teachers = World Sailing Teaching Design

World Series practical experience + teaching materials, thesis = results; Judges, referees + teachers, players = teams.

6.2.5 Transformation of achievements

Summarizing the experience of the World Championship, developing talent training programs suitable for the real work needs of enterprises, focusing on: combining practical courses with theoretical courses; combining student interests with community activities; combining selection with teaching; combining theory with practice Combined.

Through the World Skills Competition, the hotel service and management industry can accurately grasp the current status of the industry, and on this basis, it can effectively build the hotel management profession, meet the training needs of students, and cultivate high-quality technical talents. At this stage, the overall teaching reform of the tourism hotel management specialty of various colleges and universities is relatively lagging behind, and it also restricts the development of the tourism hotel management specialty in China. Therefore, the author believes that in the construction of the tourism hotel management profession, first of all, leaders should pay enough attention to this issue, and include the construction of training bases in the financial budget plan; secondly, the school should actively understand the tourism hotel management Professional training equipment and equipment change, combined with international development to introduce cutting-edge advanced equipment; Finally, we should also focus on the changes in tourism hotel management majors, so that we can improve the professional construction, and at the same time can cultivate related professionals. In terms of our educating goals are those like making up the students 'energy'^[8] and cultivating their valuable capabilities case by case, data by data and system swifiting .

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